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VIETNAMESE E-COMMERCE IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION: AN EMPIRICAL PERSPECTIVE FROM ENTERPRISES

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ABSTRACT

Digital transformation, within the context of the Fourth Industrial Revolution (Industry 4.0), is an inevitable trend for the economy in general and specifically for the field of e-commerce. In Vietnam, digital transformation in e-commerce is considered one of the top priorities outlined in the National Digital Transformation Program for 2025, with orientations extending toward 2030. Utilizing data from the Vietnam E-commerce Association (VECOM) reports and empirical studies, this paper analyzes the current state of Vietnamese e-commerce within this new context, covering its development history, human resources, online applications, and e-commerce transactions between businesses and consumers (B2C), as well as business-to-business (B2B) transactions. However, the authors also identify several challenges that e-commerce enterprises face in this digital era, including issues related to technological infrastructure, cybersecurity concerns, workforce expertise requirements, and environmental waste problems. Consequently, recommendations are proposed to support e-commerce enterprises in their growth and integration into the digital landscape.

Keywords: E-commerce; Digital transformation; VECOM; B2B; B2C

JEL codes: L81, O33, M15, L86

1. SOME BASIC CONCEPTS

1.1. Concept of E-commerce

Electronic commerce (e-commerce) refers to activities involving the buying and selling of goods, the provision of services, or the exchange of information through electronic network systems, with the internet being the most prevalent and significant platform. Specifically, these activities encompass the production, presentation, sale, insurance, distribution, and payment processes for goods and services conducted via digital platforms (Çelik & Yilmaz, 2011). In contrast to traditional commercial activities carried out at physical locations, e-commerce is distinguished by the use of web services, telecommunications, and electronic addresses to facilitate online transactions (Jizdan, 2023).

E-commerce has brought numerous substantial benefits since its inception. It provides businesses with an online trading platform on a global scale, enabling enterprises to access a broader customer base while consumers gain access to a wider variety of products (La Paz et al., 2015). Additionally, it reduces transaction costs by minimizing the time and effort required to search for goods and services, thereby increasing business efficiency (Willis, 2004). E-commerce also fosters

innovation and the development of new business models, enhancing competitive advantages for enterprises (Chen & Zhang, 2015). Despite its advantages, e-commerce poses considerable challenges, notably the necessity of implementing robust security measures and privacy protections against potential threats, such as cyberattacks and data breaches, in online transactions (La Paz et al., 2015). Furthermore, businesses engaging in e-commerce must carefully adhere to various legal frameworks across multiple jurisdictions, comply with international treaties, and follow regulations related to online trading platforms (La Paz et al., 2015).

1.2. Common types of e-commerce businesses

E-commerce encompasses various models that facilitate transactions among different entities. From a business perspective, the two most prevalent types are Business-to-Consumer (B2C) and Business-to-Business (B2B). Each type serves distinct purposes and operates under different frameworks, significantly contributing to the economy in the digital era. B2C, in particular, has received considerable media attention due to its rapid growth (Willis, 2004).

Business-to-Consumer (B2C): B2C e-commerce involves transactions between businesses and individual consumers. It is characterized by retail sales conducted over the internet. This model is commonly found on online retail platforms such as Amazon and eBay, where consumers purchase goods directly from businesses. B2C e-commerce is driven by consumer demand and is often influenced by marketing strategies and trends in consumer behavior (Aithal, 2016).

Business-to-Business (B2B): The concept of B2B e-commerce refers to electronic transactions that occur between businesses, facilitating the online buying and selling of goods and services. This model has experienced significant growth, integrating various processes such as procurement and logistics. It is particularly beneficial for micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) as it reduces transaction costs and enhances market accessibility (Ladrière et al., 2022). B2B emphasizes virtual value creation in interactions, necessitating appropriate marketing and sales strategies, especially as traditional models struggle to compete in rapidly evolving markets dominated by digital transformation platforms (Heinemann, 2020).

2. CURRENT STATUS OF VIETNAMESE E-COMMERCE ENTERPRISES IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

2.1. Overview of the Historical Development of E-commerce in Vietnam

E-commerce has undergone significant development globally since its inception in the late 1990s, marked by the establishment of the first online stores following the advent of the internet (Kasianova et al., 2022). Initially, e-commerce primarily focused on creating websites to showcase the products and services of businesses. However, due to limitations in information technology infrastructure and consumer awareness, online buying and selling activities did not significantly develop during this period. Entering the early 2000s, with the growing popularity of the internet and an increasing number of users, e-commerce began to experience notable advancements. Taobao was launched in 2003 as a C2C marketplace, quickly dominating the Chinese market and creating a stepping stone

human resources in this field to adequately meet the demands of rapid growth. Another pressing concern is the negative environmental impact resulting from e-commerce activities, particularly the plastic waste generated by product packaging. In response to these issues, since 2023, the Vietnam E-commerce Association (VECOM) has proposed a sustainable e-commerce development program aimed at bridging the digital divide, fostering high-quality digital workforce training in the context of digital transformation, and promoting environmentally responsible business practices.

2.2. Human Resources and Online Applications in E-commerce

Human resources with expertise in technology and digital transformation play a pivotal role in driving business growth in the modern era. Digital transformation significantly influences employees' mindsets while promoting sustainable practices and responsible work behaviors (Hizam et al., 2023). In Vietnam, the government introduced the National Digital Transformation Program, aiming for completion by 2025 with a vision extending to 2030 (Decision No. 749/QĐ-TTg dated June 3, 2020). This program sets numerous specific objectives related to digital human resources. Notably, by 2025, 100% of enterprises are expected to have increased awareness of digital transformation, thereby establishing a foundation for proactive training and the development of employees' digital skills (Anh & Hoang, 2023). As a result of decisive and synchronized policies, the quality of Vietnam's highly skilled technological workforce has improved significantly. According to the World Bank, Vietnam's Human Capital Index (HCI) rose from 0.66 in 2010 to 0.69 in 2020, positioning the country among the top-ranking groups in the East Asia region (Lan, 2022). A report by VECOM indicates that the prioritization of personnel with technological capabilities, e-commerce knowledge, and digital transformation skills remains consistently high among businesses, with over 60% for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and over 70% for large.

Figure 1. Priority level for using personnel with expertise in technology, e-commerce and digital transformation by enterprise size

(Source: Vietnam E-commerce Business Index (EBI) Report 2020–2024)

The year 2020 marked significant growth, underscoring the heightened demand for skilled human resources in the context of digital transformation due to the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic. This demand is expected to stabilize in the

following years. According to VECOM, sectors prioritizing the recruitment of skilled or trained personnel for digital transformation include information and communication, finance and banking, real estate, science and technology, administrative and support services, education and training, as well as arts, entertainment, and recreation.

Messaging applications such as Facebook Messenger, Zalo, Viber, and WhatsApp have played critical roles in the e-commerce activities of Vietnamese enterprises. These applications function not only as communication channels but also facilitate marketing, customer support, and online sales. As depicted in Figure 2, from 2019 to 2023, more than 50% of enterprise employees consistently utilized these digital tools in their daily tasks, with a notable surge occurring in 2020, clearly indicating the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the adoption of online communication solutions. The effective utilization of these digital technologies assists enterprises in enhancing customer engagement, improving service quality, and optimizing operational efficiency within the e-commerce sector.

Figure 2. Level of online application usage in enterprises

(Source: Vietnam E-commerce Business Index (EBI) Report 2020–2024)

Among the applications mentioned above, Facebook and Zalo are the two most frequently utilized platforms. In particular, Zalo recorded substantial usage, with over 87% of online users in 2022 and exceeding 90% in 2023, according to data published by Decision Lab. Additionally, as of 2023, Zalo had reached 76 million monthly active users, with approximately 1.8 billion messages sent daily on this platform (Minh, 2023). In contrast, other platforms such as Viber, WhatsApp, and Skype experienced comparatively lower usage and a declining number of users. This shift indicates a change in preferences among Vietnamese users, who now prioritize domestic applications that offer more locally relevant features.

Table 1. Percentage of enterprises with websites over the years

Year	Enterprises with websites (%)
2019	42%
2020	42%
2021	43%
2022	44%
2023	44%

(Source: Vietnam E-commerce Business Index (EBI) Report 2020–2024)

The survey results from VECOM indicate that the proportion of businesses with websites experienced minimal changes after 2020, with approximately 42–44% of enterprises maintaining their own websites. This demonstrates that the COVID-19 pandemic did not significantly accelerate the creation of business websites in Vietnam, as reflected in the relatively low growth rate of only 2–6% annually from 2019 to 2022. Globally, while numerous businesses intensified efforts to establish an online presence during social distancing periods, market conditions varied significantly. Many small businesses opted to utilize e-commerce platforms or social media networks instead of developing dedicated websites, resulting in minimal changes in website adoption rates.

Although not primarily focused on developing new websites, businesses are increasingly emphasizing the integration online interactive features into their existing platforms. Approximately 78% of businesses with websites have incorporated online interaction capabilities, such as Facebook and Zalo, to communicate effectively with customers. This marks a slight increase from pre-pandemic levels (approximately 73% in 2021) and is evident across both large enterprises (83%) and small-to-medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) (77%). This trend underscores the multi-channel communication strategies that businesses employ, highlighting their proactive use of social media fan pages and chat applications, in addition to traditional websites, to enhance customer engagement.

Online customer interaction methods via digital platforms encompass direct human interaction, automated chatbots, and responses generated from customer-provided information. These methods are illustrated in detail in Figure 3 below:

Figure 3. Online customer feedback form

(Source: Vietnam E-commerce Business Index (EBI) Report 2020–2024)

It is evident that despite increased investment by businesses in technology and digital transformation, human involvement continues to play a significant role. Most companies maintain dedicated teams to monitor and respond to messages or provide online customer consultations. According to a survey, approximately 77% of businesses conduct online customer interactions through direct human communication. Although this percentage is gradually decreasing due to advancements in technology and the rapid development of artificial intelligence

(AI), it remains higher compared to other interaction methods. Direct human consultation offers advantages such as flexibility and the ability to resolve complex issues, but it also involves constraints related to working hours and higher personnel costs. Consequently, the use of automated AI chatbots has emerged as a popular alternative, with approximately 50% of businesses utilizing chatbots for online customer interactions. Chatbots, either integrated into websites or platforms such as Facebook Messenger and Zalo OA, provide rapid responses to frequently asked questions without time limitations. However, they primarily handle simpler issues. Additionally, many businesses incorporate forms on their websites or social networks that allow customers to provide their contact information (email, phone number, specific requests, etc.). Employees then use this information to provide indirect responses via email or phone. This approach helps businesses maintain customer data for future interactions and integrates effectively with Customer Relationship Management (CRM) systems. According to a survey by VECOM, approximately 64% of businesses reported collecting customer contact information via their websites for subsequent interactions in 2022. However, this figure declined significantly to just 39% in 2023, reflecting the increased efficiency and rapid response capabilities enabled by advancements in AI technology.

2.3. Business-to-consumer (B2C) e-commerce transactions

Vietnam's e-commerce sector has experienced explosive growth over the past five years. In particular, online sales channels such as social networks (Facebook, Zalo, Instagram, TikTok, etc.) and e-commerce platforms (Shopee, Lazada, Tiki, etc.) are increasingly favored by many businesses. Changes in consumer behavior during the COVID-19 pandemic, coupled with technological advancements, have prompted businesses to transition to digital platforms. A summary of VECOM's report indicates that the number of businesses participating in these two platforms has steadily increased over time.

Figure 4. Percentage of enterprises engaged in business on social networks and e-commerce platforms

(Source: Vietnam E-commerce Business Index (EBI) Report 2020–2024)

The participation rate of Vietnamese enterprises in business on social networks grew significantly from 2019 to 2022. According to a survey by VECOM,

approximately 39% of enterprises engaged in business on social networks (including online forums) in 2019. This figure increased slightly to 41% in 2020 and surged to 65% in 2022, marking a peak period following the COVID-19 pandemic. Thus, while less than half of the enterprises were involved in sales through social networks in 2019, nearly two-thirds were engaged by 2022. This trend reflects the growing popularity of "social commerce" (i.e., commerce conducted on social networks) in Vietnam. Compared to other sales channels, enterprises view social networks as the most effective due to the large number of users and high potential for interaction. According to AVV (Ascend Vietnam Ventures), as of early 2022, Vietnam had approximately 77 million social media users, accounting for about 78% of the population, who used social media for an average of 2.5 hours per day. This presents a substantial potential customer base. Businesses can easily create a Facebook or Zalo page to reach buyers with minimal initial costs, allowing for flexible interactions to close sales directly. During the social distancing period of 2020-2021, many traditional stores were compelled to transition to social media, utilizing livestream sales, posting in community groups, and more, which contributed to the rapid growth of this channel. TikTok Shop, which emerged at the end of 2022, attracted a wave of businesses and individuals selling on social networks, thanks to the combination of commerce and entertainment (shopping via short videos and livestreams).

Compared to social networks, the rate of businesses participating in e-commerce platforms (such as Shopee, Lazada, Tiki, and Sendo) has also increased, although at a more modest pace. In 2019, it was estimated that only about 17% of businesses engaged in sales activities through e-commerce platforms. This figure rose to 22% in 2020, reflecting an increased willingness among businesses to explore e-commerce amid the COVID-19 pandemic.

However, growth momentum has shown signs of slowing; the participation rate remained at approximately 22% in 2021 and only slightly increased to 23% in 2022. Despite the relatively modest proportion of businesses utilizing these platforms, activities conducted through them continue to experience steady growth in scale. Revenue generated by leading e-commerce platforms has experienced significant growth in recent years. According to the metric, total sales from the four largest platforms (Shopee, Lazada, Tiki, and Sendo), along with the TikTok Shop, reached approximately 141 trillion VND (about 6 billion USD) in 2022. E-commerce platforms have become a primary sales channel for numerous retail businesses, particularly during the pandemic, when they were often the only means available to reach consumers for specific product categories. Since the pandemic, online shopping festivals have expanded in both quantity and quality, attracting substantial participation from sellers and buyers alike. Nevertheless, most small businesses remain less active on e-commerce platforms, opting instead to prioritize social media channels or direct sales methods.

Figure 5. Percentage of businesses with mobile sales applications

(Source: Vietnam E-commerce Business Index (EBI) Report 2020–2024)

According to a report by the Vietnam E-commerce Association (VECOM), the proportion of businesses utilizing mobile sales applications remains relatively low, although it has gradually increased from 2019 to 2022. Specifically, between 2019 and 2021, there was limited growth in the deployment of mobile applications: approximately 16% of businesses had mobile applications in 2019, and this figure remained nearly unchanged at around 17% in both 2020 and 2021, before rising to 22% in 2022. This slow growth can be attributed to limited human resources, particularly among small businesses during the COVID-19 pandemic, which led many companies to prioritize existing channels such as e-commerce platforms or social networks over the development of their own applications. By 2022, as online shopping demand surged with the return to normalcy post-pandemic and the acceleration of digital transformation, businesses began to focus more on mobile channels, significantly increasing the adoption rate of mobile applications. Nevertheless, as of 2023, only 20% of surveyed businesses had their own mobile applications, indicating that mobile applications are still not widely adopted and that there remains substantial potential for growth in the future.

A comprehensive analysis of advertising methods employed on websites and mobile applications by businesses engaged in business-to-consumer (B2C) e-commerce reveals that popular tools include social networks, search engines, online newspapers, emails/messages, and Key Opinion Leaders (KOLs) or Key Opinion Consumers (KOCs). Notably, social network advertising has consistently remained the preferred primary tool for businesses over the years.

Figure 6. Forms of advertising on websites and mobile applications

(Source: Vietnam E-commerce Business Index (EBI) Report 2020–2024)

Social media has consistently been a dominant advertising channel, increasing from 49% in 2019 to a peak of 59% in 2022, before slightly decreasing to 54% in 2023. This trend is reinforced by the widespread popularity of platforms such as Facebook, Zalo, TikTok, and Instagram. Data from VECOM indicates that social media advertising consistently holds the highest proportion among all online advertising types in Vietnam due to its ability to reach a large audience at a reasonable cost and its measurable effectiveness. Search engine advertising (e.g., Google Ads) fluctuated between 27% and 34% from 2019 to 2023, showing minimal variation. This stability reflects the solid, yet not overwhelming, role of search engines, which are suitable for businesses aiming to increase awareness and easily reach target customers through keywords. Advertising through Key Opinion Leaders (KOLs) and Key Opinion Consumers (KOCs) began at low levels but has demonstrated clear potential, steadily increasing over time. Consumer behavior indicates a growing trust in authentic, experience-based content shared by real individuals, as opposed to traditional advertisements. Although still emerging, this form of advertising is highly effective, particularly for targeting younger audiences on platforms such as TikTok, Instagram, and YouTube.

In contrast to the growth and coverage of the aforementioned advertising forms, the remaining two are not widely implemented and even show a tendency to decrease in reach. For online newspapers, this channel experienced a sharp decline from 24%-25% during the period of 2019-2020 to just 14% in 2023. Similarly, advertising through email and text messages has continuously decreased from 29% in 2019 to 18% in 2023. It is evident that consumers are increasingly avoiding traditional advertising content in online newspapers and emails, as well as network messages with similar content. Additionally, increasingly stringent anti-spam regulations (Decree 91/2020 on anti-spam messages) have made businesses more cautious when utilizing bulk SMS. Consequently, these forms of advertising are likely to remain at a low level in the future.

2.4. Business-to-Business (B2B) E-commerce Transactions

In the era of digital transformation, B2B businesses are increasingly utilizing digital platforms and technologies to interact and conduct transactions. This includes the use of software for human resource management (HRM), supply chain management (SCM), customer relationship management (CRM), and enterprise resource planning (ERP). Additionally, businesses are digitizing processes through electronic contracts, invoices, and signatures, as well as implementing online payment methods such as internet banking, payment cards, and e-wallets. The application of technology in these processes enables businesses to work more efficiently, minimize resource usage, and achieve greater productivity.

Figure 7. Trends in using management software in businesses

(Source: Vietnam E-commerce Business Index (EBI) Report 2020–2024)

Based on the chart above, it is clear that accounting and financial software has been the most widely used tool, maintaining a stable usage rate for many years. On average, approximately 90% of businesses utilized this software during the statistical period, highlighting its essential role and priority status within companies' digitalization efforts. This widespread adoption can be partly attributed to the impact of Decree 123/2020/ND-CP, which mandates the legal requirement for electronic invoices, thereby necessitating the use of electronic accounting software to comply with regulations. Human resource management (HRM) software, which is a traditional management tool, also had a relatively high usage rate of over 50% in previous periods, although it has not recently shown significant growth. Additionally, in recent years, rapid advancements in artificial intelligence (AI) have enabled many businesses to reduce management costs in this area, slightly reducing its usage rate; nevertheless, HRM remains an indispensable tool. Other digital tools employed by B2B enterprises, such as SCM, CRM, and ERP, currently have lower adoption rates. This is mainly due to concerns about high implementation and operational costs (particularly ERP and SCM) compared with perceived benefits. In addition, there are not many knowledgeable personnel to manage and develop this software because this field is relatively new. However, given their critical role in the context of digital transformation, businesses are likely to focus increasingly on adopting these tools. At the announcement ceremony of the "Business digital

transformation support program for 2021–2025" held on December 3, 2024, by the Ministry of Planning and Investment, the goal was set to ensure that every business gains access to digital solutions and heightened awareness of digital transformation by 2025. At that time, such software solutions are expected to become mandatory standards for enterprises in the new era-the digitalization era.

One clear indication of digital transformation in the e-commerce industry is the gradual replacement of traditional paper documents with online formats, notably electronic invoices, electronic contracts, and electronic signatures in B2B transactions. The use of electronic documents has increasingly become standard practice in recent years, particularly following the COVID-19 pandemic. These digital technologies enable businesses to sign agreements and manage invoices entirely within a digital environment, significantly saving time and costs while enhancing operational efficiency.

Figure 8. Trends in using electronic contracts/signatures/invoices in businesses
(Source: Vietnam E-commerce Business Index (EBI) Report 2020–2024)

Recognizing the aforementioned benefits, the trend of utilizing electronic contracts, signatures, and invoices in B2B enterprises has been steadily increasing. The VECOM report indicates a continuous rise in this trend, with 60% of surveyed enterprises reporting their use in 2019; by 2023, this figure had escalated to 90%. In a world significantly impacted by digital transformation, this shift is essential. Notably, the COVID-19 pandemic has served as a pivotal moment, compelling many organizations to adopt electronic signature solutions, resulting in a 50% increase in the number of enterprises utilizing e-signatures in a short period (Andre, 2022). Many organizations are now pursuing comprehensive digital transformation, embracing the "digital-first" trend, where the digitization of contracts and documents is an unavoidable step (Andre, 2022). According to Corcentric, (2023), due to compliance pressures and the advantages of combating tax fraud, numerous governments-including Vietnam-are mandating the electronic processing of documents to enhance transparency and prevent VAT revenue losses. Consequently, businesses must adapt, making the adoption of electronic invoices inevitable. Fueled by digital transformation, legal policies, and market demands, the use of electronic contracts, invoices, and signatures is likely to remain a dominant trend in the coming years.

For business-to-business (B2B) e-commerce transactions, selecting an appropriate payment method is crucial. The survey results from VECOM indicate that, despite ongoing integration into the digital transformation context, businesses still favor traditional payment methods such as cash and internet banking. Approximately 90% of the businesses surveyed utilize these two payment methods as their primary means of transaction. Other methods, such as payment cards, e-wallets, and mobile/SMS accounts, have not yet been widely adopted.

Table 2. Payment methods in businesses

Year	Cash	Internet Banking	Payment Card	E-wallet	Mobile/SMS Account
2021	89%	86%	30%	20%	5%
2022	89%	89%	32%	28%	7%
2023	87%	86%	28%	22%	10%

(Source: Vietnam E-commerce Business Index (EBI) Report 2020–2024)

For large transactions, bank transfer payments are still preferred due to their convenience, transparency, and ease of transaction management, which align with the digital financial management model prioritized by B2B enterprises. Payments via cards or e-wallets are not widely adopted because of limitations on transaction limits and high transaction fees compared to internet banking. Additionally, the government has introduced various policies encouraging businesses to engage in cashless transactions and prioritize digital payment methods (Tuan, 2024).

3. CHALLENGES FOR VIETNAM'S E-COMMERCE IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

E-commerce in Vietnam is experiencing strong growth within the context of digital transformation; however, limitations related to technological infrastructure still hinder the sustainable and comprehensive development of this sector. According to VECOM's 2023 report, although internet network quality has improved, coverage remains uneven, particularly in rural and mountainous areas, significantly restricting e-commerce activities. Delivering goods to rural and remote regions remains challenging because of underdeveloped logistics and transportation infrastructures. This results in lengthy delivery times and elevated operating costs, limiting e-commerce expansion into nonurban areas (B-Company, 2025). Additionally, the rapid expansion of digital technology has intensified information security concerns, with increasing cyberattacks targeting businesses. A survey by the Vietnam Information Technology Emergency Response Center (VNCERT) reported nearly 10,000 website attacks in Vietnam requiring intervention, approximately 50% of which involved malware exploiting security vulnerabilities (Thuy & Duong, 2024). Moreover, the electronic payment infrastructure is still incomplete. According to the General Statistics Office (2023), only approximately 40% of people use electronic payment methods, which is a significantly lower rate than that reported by regional countries such as Thailand (68%) and Malaysia (75%). The lack of synchronization between payment platforms and e-commerce enterprises complicates system integration, thereby reducing the efficiency of online business operations.

The next challenge for the development of Vietnam's e-commerce sector during this period was the growing demand for highly skilled and knowledgeable human resources. This need arises from the increasing number of businesses entering the e-commerce market, leading to higher recruitment demands. Human resources also serve as a crucial pillar in constructing an e-commerce assessment index, which includes criteria such as the capacity to meet appropriate human resource requirements and the priority given to hiring skilled or professionally trained personnel. According to the Ministry of Industry and Trade, Vietnam has been internationally recognized as the fastest-growing digital economy in Southeast Asia as of 2023 (Van Phuc, 2024). Nevertheless, the country is currently experiencing a significant shortage of qualified human resources required to sustain this rapid growth. Statistical forecasts indicate that by 2025, Vietnam could face a shortage of approximately 200,000 digital technology workers, potentially rising to 220,000 by 2026 unless substantial improvements in training and education are implemented promptly (Van Phuc, 2024). In addition, according to VECOM's report, only approximately 30% of human resources in e-commerce enterprises are formally trained, whereas the remaining 70% originate from related fields such as business administration, trade, and information technology. Clearly, Vietnam is facing a critical deficit of highly specialized human resources within its e-commerce enterprises.

The rapid development of e-commerce has raised significant environmental concerns, primarily because packaging and transportation result in large amounts of plastic waste, thus exacerbating pollution levels. Specifically, plastic and nylon materials from packaging, if improperly managed, can lead to long-term pollution of soil, water, and ecosystems. Currently, Vietnam's plastic waste recycling rate remains relatively low, meaning that most packaging materials from e-commerce activities are at risk of being buried or released into the natural environment (Van Hau, 2024). According to the 2024 VECOM E-commerce Index Report, the volume of plastic packaging and related materials used in Vietnam's e-commerce sector reached approximately 170,000 tons in 2023. Given the stable annual growth rate of over 25% in the e-commerce industry, it is projected that by 2030, the plastic waste generated by e-commerce activities will significantly amplify the environmental challenges faced by Vietnam.

4. SOME POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

First, with respect to the development of technological infrastructure, the government needs to increase investments in building and improving telecommunications and internet infrastructure in Vietnam, particularly by increasing service quality and expanding coverage in rural and remote areas. This initiative aims to facilitate equitable and effective access for e-commerce enterprises, given the significant development disparity in e-commerce between Hanoi, Ho Chi Minh City, and other localities—an issue explicitly highlighted in the VECOM report for the 2020–2024 period. Infrastructure is considered one of the core pillars that must be prioritized and proactively developed—this is one of the key targets identified in Resolution No. 57-NQ/TW dated December 22, 2024, issued by

the Politburo on breakthroughs in developing science, technology, innovation, and national digital transformation. Infrastructure development must be accompanied by financial resources; therefore, the state should implement relevant support policies, such as tax exemptions or reductions, for enterprises investing in technology to increase business growth. This should further encourage enterprises to increase investments in cybersecurity and develop advanced information security technological solutions in the context of ongoing globalization. Additionally, to ensure effective collaboration among banks, payment intermediaries, and e-commerce enterprises, the government should promptly establish and promulgate a unified set of standards regarding personal data used in electronic payment accounts.

With respect to the development of highly skilled human resources, further strengthening supportive policies aimed at promoting and expanding specialized training programs in e-commerce across universities, colleges, and vocational training centers is imperative. Many universities and colleges have already begun enrollment and produced their first cohorts of graduates in e-commerce, digital marketing, and digital business-related fields. Thus, it is feasible to upgrade these programs to higher levels of education, such as master's degrees, in these specializations. These training programs should emphasize effectively integrating theory and practical application, to meet real labor market demands. At the same time, it is essential to enhance collaboration between educational institutions and enterprises in digital transformation, with VECOM serving as a bridge. This collaboration will help ensure that personnel trained in these areas are increasingly equipped with practical, industry-relevant skills. Businesses, for their part, should proactively plan and implement internal training programs, thereby enhancing their employees' digital transformation skills and adaptability to the increasingly high requirements set by the ongoing digital transformation context.

The third recommendation is related to environmental management and reducing plastic waste generated from e-commerce activities. Enterprises should transition to environmentally friendly packaging solutions, such as reusable or biodegradable materials—for example, replacing plastic bags and boxes with recycled paper packaging or eliminating unnecessary packaging materials altogether. On the governmental side, it is essential to establish a clear legal framework and provide support to e-commerce businesses proactively researching and implementing innovative solutions aimed at minimizing plastic waste arising from product packaging and delivery. Additionally, the government should develop a set of criteria to evaluate and identify green e-commerce businesses on the basis of sustainable e-commerce models. Furthermore, increasing the implementation of communication campaigns aimed at increasing consumer awareness of the negative environmental impacts caused by plastic waste is crucial to encouraging more responsible consumer behaviors.

The above policy recommendations will contribute to minimizing negative impacts on the environment and solving social issues related to human resources and technological infrastructure, thereby creating a favourable environment and

ensuring that e-commerce businesses in Vietnam can develop quickly, sustainably and comprehensively in the future.

5. CONCLUSION

In the context of increasingly widespread digital transformation, Vietnam's e-commerce sector has experienced robust growth, gradually becoming an essential driver of the country's digital economy. An analysis of reports by the Vietnam E-commerce Association, as well as practical observations, indicate that enterprises are increasingly focused on developing specialized human resources and enhancing online communication tools. In B2C transactions, businesses actively engage with customers on digital platforms, establish sales channels on e-commerce marketplaces, and fully utilize various online advertising channels. Similarly, B2B enterprises are progressively adopting software solutions for management purposes, and the electronic processing of contracts, invoices, and documents has become nearly universal. These efforts have significantly contributed to improved business efficiency, market expansion, and enhanced customer experiences amid digital transformation. However, Vietnam's e-commerce industry still faces notable challenges, particularly related to digital infrastructure, cybersecurity, highly skilled human resources, and environmental concerns. To facilitate the rapid, sustainable growth of Vietnamese e-commerce and its deeper integration into the global digital economy, governmental authorities must proactively build and refine a comprehensive, transparent legal framework, promoting digital transformation in enterprises alongside environmental protection initiatives. Additionally, prioritizing investments in technological infrastructure, high-quality human resource training, and strengthened information security are prerequisites for Vietnam to fully leverage the benefits of e-commerce in the digital era.

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